

Protocol for registration

05 March 2024 8:58 AM

I am basing this on the PRISMA protocol I did for a realist review because it asks useful questions and made me think when I did it then, but will freely disregard irrelevant aspects of the form as it is not really designed for content analysis and rather systematic reviews

<https://www.crd.york.ac.uk/PROSPERO/documents/PROSPERO%20registration%20form.pdf>

1. Review title
 - a. Tracing the role of news outlets in the rise of a conspiracy theory: Hydroxychloroquine in the early days of COVID-19
2. Anticipated or actual start date
 - a. 04/03/2024
3. Anticipated completion date
 - a. 30/04/2024
4. Stage of review at time of submission
 - a. Preliminary searches are started and completed
 - b. Piloting of the study selection process is started but not completed
 - c. Formal screening of search results against eligibility criteria is unstarted
 - d. Data extraction is unstarted
 - e. Risk of bias (quality) assessment is unstarted
 - f. Data analysis is unstarted
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9. Organisational affiliation of the review
 - a. University of Sussex
10. Review team members and their organisational affiliations
 - a. Elizabeth Ford. Brighton and Sussex Medical School.
 - b. Harm Van Marwijk. Brighton and Sussex Medical School.
 - c. Dominique Makowski. University of Sussex School of Psychology
11. Funding sources
 - a. Self-funded
12. Conflicts of interest
 - a. None to report
13. Collaborators
 - a. Katie Goddard. Brighton and Sussex Medical School.
14. Review question
 - a. **How did news media portrayals of Hydroxychloroquine in the period immediately following its rise to popularity (17 - 19 March 2020) contribute to the subsequent rise of conspiracism and the spread of this essential piece of misinformation?**
 - b. Subquestions:
 - i. Did coverage of hydroxychloroquine in this time period differ substantially by political ideology (proxied via political ideological ranking of the news outlet)?
 - ii. How did the US public health apparatus attempt to combat this misinformation in this

time period?

15. Searches

a. Search terms

The following search terms are performed as Boolean searching within the Nexis NEWS database:

"publication(daily caller OR spectator OR newsbusters OR Fox news OR national review OR weekly standard OR realclearpolitics OR FORBES OR National interest OR associated press OR Politico OR CNN OR new york times OR newsweek OR guardian OR new yorker OR salon OR quartz OR the nation OR vanity fair OR Prospect) and hydroxychloroquine"

b. Sources

i. Nexis

A 40-year archive of more than 40,000 curated news and business sources. Nexis strategically collates trusted premium and web news, company profiles, legal content and industry information. Data is standardised and indexed for ease and speed.

c. Search dates

i. 17 March 2020 - 31 March 2020

- 1) Hydroxychloroquine rose quickly to public awareness alongside social media and public statements coming from Elon Musk (17 March 2020) and Donald Trump (19 March 2020). This content analysis focuses on the period (two weeks) immediately following this rise in public awareness to investigate the role of the news media in the creation of this conspiracy theory and the dissemination of misinformation. More information available here:

<https://openaccess.city.ac.uk/id/eprint/27960/3/>

d. Restrictions

i. Language: English

English has a wide body of literature on the topic and is the predominant fluent language of the research team. This project does not have capacity for translation in the literature review.

ii. Publication period: 17 March 2020 - 31 March 2020

- 1) Hydroxychloroquine rose quickly to public awareness alongside social media and public statements coming from Elon Musk (17 March 2020) and Donald Trump (19 March 2020). This content analysis focuses on the period (two weeks) immediately following this rise in public awareness to investigate the role of the news media in the creation of this conspiracy theory and the dissemination of misinformation. More information available here:

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iii. News outlets

- 1) In order to answer RQ2, the following framework was utilised to identify a range of news outlets that sit on distinct points on the spectrum of political ideology alignment while also being available on Nexis: <https://osf.io/ch8gi/download>. The news outlets chosen and their position on the political ideology alignment spectrum are as follows:

Far-right (2-3 on the Ideology of Online News Media scale)

Daily Caller

The Spectator

Newsbusters.org

Right (1-2 on the Ideology of Online News Media scale)

Fox News

National review

Weekly Standard

Center-right (.5-1 on the Ideology of Online News Media scale)
 National interest
 Realclearpolitics
 Forbes

Center (-0.5-0.5 on the Ideology of Online News Media scale)
 Associated Press
 Politico
 CNN

Center-left (-0.5 -> -1 on the Ideology of Online News Media scale)
 NY Times
 Newsweek
 The Guardian

Left (-1 -> -2 on the Ideology of Online News Media scale)
 New yorker (could also be center-left)
 Salon.com
 Quartz

Far-left (-2 -> -3 on the Ideology of Online News Media scale)
 The Nation
 Vanity fair
 Prospect

iv. Whether searches will be re-run prior to final analysis

1) No

16. Condition or domain being studied

a. Reporting potential use of hydroxychloroquine as alternative medicine for COVID-19

17. Interventions

a. Public health apparatus responses to this rise in public awareness (to be studied separately from this searching). These responses as interventions against misinformation and conspiracism are systematically reviewed as laid out in the realist review pre-registered in PROSPERO available at the following link:

https://www.crd.york.ac.uk/PROSPERO/display_record.php?RecordID=440580

18. Comparators/control

a. News media reviewed will be compared to public health apparatus responses (interventions) to and against the rise of public awareness of, misinformation about, and growing conspiracism regarding hydroxychloroquine as laid out in number 17.

19. Types of sources to be included

a. This study includes print news media from a range of political ideology alignments as discussed in number 15diii

20. Context

a. Early in the COVID-19 pandemic, hydroxychloroquine was initially considered and tested as a potential medical intervention to alleviate COVID-19 (Sattui et al. 2020). This involved considerable rapidity in testing and the use of preprints to expedite the scientific process. In the case of hydroxychloroquine, overinterpretation and amplification of preliminary results outside of the scientific community - followed by attempted corrective measures by the public health apparatuses - created a pendulum effect in which public discourses were initially very supportive of hydroxychloroquine but then swung back far enough to create a backfire effect (for more information see Sattui et al. 2020). This backfire effect is theorised in the misinformation literature to occur when fact-checking or other attempts to dissuade someone of strongly held, politically polarised beliefs, misalign with the worldview of that person to such an extent as to reinforce their pre-existing beliefs and degrade trust in the legitimate institutions attempting to correct/inform them (Van der Linden 2022). Baker & Maddox (2022) extend this idea here by tracing how the politicisation and sudden rise to public awareness of hydroxychloroquine contributed to a backfire effect in the reactive

debunking attempts of the public health apparatus.

This study will investigate the role of the US news media in this rise to public awareness and conspiracism around hydroxychloroquine in March 2020. It will explore whether differences in political ideology alignment among media outlets impacted reporting, usage of language, and message framing on this topic. It will further examine the public health apparatus response and utilise the knowledge developed in the realist review discussed in 17a to analyse effectiveness of this intervention and discuss whether changes could have potentially improved its effectiveness.

21. Data extraction

a. Eligibility criteria

i. Relevance

The most primary criteria for eligibility is relevance to the topic: namely, some media can be excluded as being not about hydroxychloroquine in the context of an alternative COVID-19 medicine and the public awareness and conspiracism around that topic. Alternatively, if the media makes only a passing reference to the topic or is fundamentally about something else, that media would be excluded.

ii. Quality

Secondary eligibility is quality of the media. For instance, if the media has poor language use, unclear argumentation, lack of clarity, or writing errors that inhibit readability, that media may be excluded.

b. Study selection

- i. One reviewer will screen for inclusion, with team members checking their decisions.
- ii. Disagreements between judgments will be resolved through team discussion, with final say going to the reviewer.
- iii. Tracking through Excel will record decisions.

c. Data extraction

- i. One reviewer will extract the data, with team members checking the data.
- ii. Disagreements between judgments will be resolved through team discussion, with final say going to the reviewer.
- iii. Missing data will be excluded from analysis. Study investigators of studies missing data will not be contacted.
- iv. Data will be recorded through OneNote, Excel, and NVivo

d. Coding

- i. Codes will be developed a priori through a synthesis of codes developed iteratively through the realist review referenced above in 17a as well as codes from similar contemporary content analysis articles and arising from the theoretical literature in this area.

22. Strategy for data synthesis

The strategy for data synthesis for this project centres on content analysis. More specifically, quantitative analysis involving keyword searching and manual coding performed using a priori codes. This approach is well established in the literature, with recent trends towards interpretative approaches as opposed to directly quantitative approaches that simply count codes (Graneheim et al. 2017). This study follows this trend, pursuing interpretative analysis from the coding process more so than simply reporting keyword and code counts. Stemler (2015) notes that content analysis is in a renaissance today due to the prevalence of varied recorded data and the need for methods to incorporate and handle varied data. Content analysis offers both the flexibility and capacity for investigating the extent of a noted or hypothesised macro-scale social phenomenon required for the analysis within this study.

Content analysis takes a wide view to investigate the extent of codes within a corpus of

varied data (Harwood & Garry 2003). In this study, this looks like a priori codes developed from the existing literature, relevant theories, and the realist review noted in 17a. A contemporary example of a published content analysis journal article on a similar topic is Holt et al. (2022) in which online expressions of political ideology were examined through keyword quantitative analysis and qualitative interpretative approaches. Their use of content analysis to determine the constructed patterns of meaning across a large sample (ibid) highlights and exemplifies the goals of content analysis as is planned for this study. A further example of a similar paper is Ogbodo et al. (2020) who uses content analysis to examine global media framing of COVID-19 using pre-determined coding frames. Their analysis focused on exclusively the largest global media outlets and their framing of COVID-19 overall, whereas this study focuses on smaller US-centric media outlets following a framework of political ideology alignment and their framing of hydroxychloroquine within the larger COVID-19 pandemic. Nonetheless, much of the methodological nuances from Ogbodo et al. (2020) can be applied to this study. Content analysis of media coverage can be aligned with constructionist frame perspectives that view media as an information processor which creates interpretative packages to reflect and then add to the culture surrounding an issue with substantial media coverage. These interpretative packages then dominate both media coverage of the issue and public audience responses thereto. In this study, this constructionist framing used by Ogbodo et al. (2020) similarly applies to investigating how the US media framed and influenced public perceptions of hydroxychloroquine and the subsequent conspiracism and misinformation that arose around it.

The consecutive days sampling format as laid out in Riffe, Aust, and Lacy (1993) justifies the small sampling window of this study. They showed that small samples using consecutive days of coverage can be sufficient for understanding broader news content over a period of time. In this study, the narrow temporal bounds chosen for data inclusion criteria matches the spike in public awareness of hydroxychloroquine and the rise of conspiracism and misinformation that came alongside that public awareness. Practically, the narrow temporal bounding also helps make the number of data items for analysis manageable for the author.

Following the recommendations of Stemler (2015), this study plans to utilise bayesian statistical analysis of the language within the included news media alongside the codes themselves to derive empirical insights into the extent of codes and the hypothesised phenomenon they represent within the data.

23. Analysis of subgroups or subsets
 - a. Subgroup analysis is planned on each group of news media outlets by political ideological alignment as laid out in number 15diii. These subgroups will then be analysed comparatively to answer RQ2.
24. Method of the study: content analysis
25. Language: English
26. Country: USA
27. Other registration details: N/A
28. URL for published protocol: N/A
29. Dissemination plans

In addition to producing a chapter for a PhD thesis at the University of Sussex which will be made available free of charge on the University website and a variety of PhD thesis archives, a paper will be submitted to a leading journal in this field to further disseminate the results of this content analysis.
30. Keywords: content analysis, COVID-19, hydroxychloroquine, conspiracy theories, misinformation, news media, political ideology
31. Details of existing studies of the same topic by the same authors:

https://www.crd.york.ac.uk/PROSPERO/display_record.php?RecordID=440580

32. Additional information

This review is occurring as part of a PhD candidacy at Brighton and Sussex Medical School to inform the other analytical projects within the PhD candidacy.

33. Details of final report/publication: N/A

References:

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